

SETTLED INTO QUICKSILVER: A CHOREOGRAPHIC PROCESS

by

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Table of Contents

Introduction.....2

Written Journals.....3

Video Journals.....14

Final Reflection.....14

Final Production.....17

Works Cited.....17

Introduction

The topic I focused on for this project is the choreographic process. More specifically, I focused on different approaches to choreography. This topic is personally important to me because I have been dancing all my life, and choreography has played a large role in how I dance today. The performance side is the aspect that I enjoy the most when it comes to dance, so I wanted to see if that enjoyment could be found in the choreography aspect as well. At this point in my life, I plan on becoming a dance teacher after I graduate college. Since this is my career goal, I would be teaching and choreographing multiple dances every season. I would need to have the knowledge of choreography and different ways to approach it. This is important to the people and dancers in my field because not all dancers plan to be choreographers. Through this project, I explored the choreographic processes by six influential choreographers, and applied it to my own process. I kept written and video journals to document my process and concluded through a written reflection and a final performance. By having the knowledge of different choreographic processes, I would be able to utilize each one to benefit the particular dance I need to create at that moment. My goal for this project was to educate myself on the complicated art that is choreography, and be able to apply all of the tools and techniques that I have learned to my own process, setting me up for the most successful career I can achieve.

Written Journals

Shp research

Wayne McGregor

- pictures movement
- brings inapo to life
 - ↳ "TED" = movement

Intra:

- no limits
- hyperextension of movements
- large arches of body
- extension of legs

Alexander technique

- explored:

- improv, somatics, dance ethnography, Alex. tech.
- blended together

DO I
NEED THIS?

Graham

- "breaks the rules"
- contraction & release
- shift of weight
- dramatic

Alvin Ailey

- combination of techniques
 - ↳ lower body ballet (articulate & long)
 - upper body modern (less restrictive)
 - ↳ jazz, social, culture
 - ↳ athletic
- technique is utilized, not the focus

ADT

- out of the box
- quick, odd, ragged, uneasy
- doesn't fall under a category
- pretty & "ugly" elements
- breaks rules

Paul Taylor

- clear rhythmic phrasing
- traditional
- limited use of steps
 - repeats & rearranged
 - visual & rhythmic effect
- logical
- sculptural & groupings
- horizontal & vertical movement contrast
- *accidents*
- humor & satire

Trisha Brown

- post modern
- bones, grounded
- plays w/ improv & the individual

Isadora Duncan

- inspired by waves
- Greek influence
- sculptures
- flowy, graceful, picture worthy

Videoshave

- paul taylor
- wayne mcgreggor
- ADT
- graham

don't have

- duncan (prob wont find)
- trisha brown
- alvin ailey

Extra info found along the way

- saved instagram post

Choreography layout

- Pacific - myself
- Atlantic - taylor & ailey
- Indian - wayne & graham
- * Arctic - trisha & ADT
- Southern - duncan

New Songs *

- #1 duncan
- #2 taylor & ailey
- #3 wayne & graham
- #4 trisha
- #5 myself

Starting Over w/ Songs...

1st song - ocean sounds mainly
give off a peaceful vibe
blends into the next piece

2nd song - something more individualistic?
something more uneasy? *starm a' brunn'*
blends into next song

3rd song - something more dramatic
emotion pour out here

4th song - a falling action of some sort?
more of an acceptance feel?

blend

5th song - a resolution type feel
going to bed / finishing off the day?
ocean @ night feel

Journal #1

for this session, my goal was to create some choreography, but mainly focus on how I want the pieces to flow. I listened to each song a couple times, figuring out where I want each choreographic process to fit. I started choreographing today without a starting point in mind. I chose a simple movement and kept creating from that moment on. The movement that I produced came from a place of comfort. It all logically flowed. I wanted to see where my weight wanted to go or how my arms and legs naturally wanted to move. Because this movement vocabulary is practiced in our technique classes, I was able to feel comfortable and it helped me create movement quicker. I felt calm while creating this time. I hope that is how I feel as I continue this journey.

Journal #2

my goal for today was to finish the choreography for the 1st phrase. I know I will need to clean everything down the line, but for now, what I have is a good start. After trying to piece it together slowly, I feel good about it and happy with it so far. The movement I have settled on is slow and undulated. I haven't had the chance to think about how to put this onto a group of dancers, but

I will have time to think on it later. I envision some moments of rippled movement and possibly Cannons, but that is all I can see as of now.

Journal #3

- now I have to figure things out conceptually...
- what I originally had planned, I am either not liking or I need something to drive the storyline
- abstract art is brilliant, but in this case, I need a plan, or @ least an arc.
- this reversal time, I'm spending it rethinking and developing my concept.
- I'm keeping the ocean theme, but creating a storyline behind it
- I have to figure out new songs...

Song ideas

- Arctic by sleeping at last
- water lilies by a teardrop in the lake
- into the deepend by the purple stripe

1st song : about 1 person
 2-3 middle songs: flashback / journey
 last song: conclusion

Journal #4

Start walking in silence/waves. Start dancing on 2nd set of piano notes

A starts the walking 1st.
 → D comes in when A starts dancing
 L comes in when D starts dancing

goal for this section is to move from the solar plexus movement is allowed to be slow and sustained

this formation comes after they move when they dance together
 from here, I think I will go into rippled movement from front to back to create an element of excitement before the more intense stuff.

Journal #5

Arcoiris choreo:

^x ^x
mad & ame

^x
ali

- start combo 0:50 end combo 1:40
- maddie does combo while ali catches up & speeds ahead? amelia does something moving around the spall
 - maybe ali does floor work / can't fit in last piece?
 - once ali gets off floor, she joins w/ amelia to form a diagonal line

Journal #6

CORRECTIONS FROM 1st rehearsal

- make sure to go to specific spots I gave
- wait until the last second to get to your spot
- go over pathway & timing w/amelia
- really milk 1st section
- clearly figure out facings after aracado picking
- release the head & let the movement come from the chest & shoulder blades
- keep the focus out/up to give an external feel not internal
- ali, do 4 waves, slowly bring arms down to repeat beginning. focus on hands
- maddie do 2 waves, amelia do 3 before repeating beginning
 - ↳ make their way to each other in the back corner SL

Chorus to continue phrase #2

after the ↗ ↘ section, come to a line in the middle ↙ of the stage

do rippled movement @ different levels

↳ leads to breaking off / frantic running till I is left on stage

• collaborate w/dancers

give time for them to create

a little phrase they feel from the music w/ intention of utilizing the bones.

phase #3

Journal # 7

Choreo ideas: for the transition from the 2nd to the 3rd piece, I want everyone to be in some sort of line, or clump, making direct focus on the last note. Then when it goes into the next, I want them to look around in different directions and start collapsing in on themselves. I want it to start off very graham like & visceral. See if everyone can do May 3rd for .

Journal # 8

- have all build the anticipation & the suspension. make it extra tense & dramatic.
- see what everyone has for their homework
- run to spots before group section
- after lift with the kick,
- do partnerwork to create relationships
- do a fast ripple section
- get up & pull each other around the stage to start next section

Final piece

- after the rock, take the next steps different sections

- make everyone face the center for the fort things
- turn face the front to do the next bit fill the floor section

- Sissy moves more than A or M so she can end up in the center

- for the very end, A walks off first, then M, then S.

Video Journals

<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/249i1plgklnxg8p/AABDarNoMDNE7VD3fyml-WZha?dl=0>

Final Reflection

The process of choreographing a 20 minute piece and exploring different elements to the choreographic process was a lot more work than I intended it to be. Originally, I thought that as long as I gave myself a certain set of parameters, I would have plenty of ideas and movements to piece together in the process. Actually, that was quite the opposite. I found myself at a creation block after about three eight counts of movement. Since this project was to explore other choreographers' processes to see what my own process could be, it made the journey harder than I thought it would. I realized that there are aspects of each choreographers' process that I found useful, but creating a whole dance based on their style was overwhelming. When I came to terms with it, I decided that the last phrase on this project would be created based on what I learned and what came most naturally to me. Not only did I learn about myself in terms of choreography, I also learned a lot about my work ethic and how I document my choreography.

One of the first things that I noticed about my personal process was my preference for documenting my feelings and thoughts. At the beginning of the project, I established that I would keep written journals to show my experience. I quickly found that I would gravitate towards video journals. I would prop my phone up and hit record before I would begin choreographing. I realized that I was able to stay in tune with my mind and body easier when I only focused on choreographing and not thinking about writing down every single detail. My written journals started off being very descriptive of how I felt about

each time I sat down to choreograph. By the end of my project, the journal entries became more shorthand and quick little notes for where I wanted to take my choreography next. I find that the video journals show more about how I was feeling in the moment because I can physically see how certain movements would form and the times where I felt amazing about the movement I created. The videos also show how frustrated I would get while choreographing. There are many moments that I captured of me just lying on the floor, contemplating the project as a whole. I was also able to capture the overwhelming moments that turned into random movement that's only purpose was to release the stress and frustration. Another thing that I was able to capture with the video journals was the progress at which the entire piece came together. Even though everything has separate clips, they all individually show development. Once I started the rehearsal process with other dancers, I was able to film the final run of each rehearsal, which allowed me to look at the dancers progress as well as the overall picture coming together. At this point of the project, the written journals were only utilized for notes/corrections for my dancers and for the random ideas that would pop up throughout rehearsals.

As for the choreographic process, the one thing that was able to keep me from giving up was to keep going back to the videos and research I did at the beginning. There were many points throughout this semester where I would just be lying in bed, stressing about how I was going to finish the dance. Each time I was able to get myself out of those little funks by going back to the original video that inspired me to go through with this project. The amount of times I would pull up Wayne McGregor's TedTalk about choreography is astonishing. I never go out of my way to watch TedTalks, but each time I

would watch this one, new ways of exploring my choreography would come up and I would have about two hours of inspiration and motivation to create more movement. Each time I would get stuck while choreographing for the phrases based on other choreographers, I would stop and think about the research I had on their work ethic. Even though some phrases took me longer to create than others, in the end, I was able to have a finished product that I was satisfied with.

Some of the moments in this process that stuck out to me were all of the times where I felt lost and wanted to keep pushing the project off. I knew I would have times through this process that would make me feel this way, but I didn't expect just how often it would happen and how much it would affect the project overall. The second phrase of my project took the longest to choreograph. This is because I had the least motivation for this particular section. Each time I would go to create movement for it, I would end up not liking what I came up with. So, I would throw the movement away and re-choreograph. The problem with this was that I would quickly become unmotivated and stop for the day. I wouldn't come back to the piece for several days, which in turn pushed back the process even farther. Eventually, I was able to come up with something that I was satisfied with, but at this point the movement is not my favorite. I do plan on revisiting this dance in the future when I have a larger group of dancers, so I am sure I will have some choreographic inspiration to reconfigure the parts that I was not happy with originally. I know that I could have had more development within my choreography and my process, but given the amount of pieces I put on myself, I can confidently say that I am happy with what I was able to accomplish over the course of a year.

Final Production

<https://youtu.be/htJnO7pQWtQ>

Works Cited

- “A choreographer’s creative process in real time.” *Ted*, uploaded by TEDGlobal, June 12, https://www.ted.com/talks/wayne_mcgregor_a_choreographer_s_creative_process_in_real_time?utm_campaign=tedsread&utm_medium=referral&utm_source=tedcomshare
- “Australian Dance Theatre: Be Yourself - Highlights.” *Youtube*, uploaded by Australian Dance Theatre, Nov. 27, 2013. <https://youtu.be/GaqeVi-DyBM>
- Liska, Suzanne. “Somatic Ethnographic Research: A Choreographic Process Informed by Alexander Technique.” *Choreographic Practices*, vol. 11, no. 1, May 2020, pp. 75–99. *EBSCOhost*, doi:10.1386/chor_00013_1.
- Dance Spirit. “Graham Technique.” *Dance Spirit*, Dance Spirit, 11 Feb. 2021, www.dancespirit.com/graham_technique-2326036529.html.
- deLahunta, Scott, and Beth V. Jordan. "Through the Lens of Choreographic Process." *Arts Marketing*, vol. 10, no. 1, 2020, pp. 53-64. *ProQuest*, <https://www-proquest-com.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/scholarly-journals/through-lens-choreographic-process/docview/2498985612/se-2?accountid=9840>, doi:<http://dx.doi.org.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/10.1108/AAM-07-2019-0024>.
- “Excerpt from ‘Speaking In Tongues.’” *Youtube*, uploaded by Howard Roseman, Nov. 20, 2017. <https://youtu.be/cAKYwxU39-Y>.
- “FAR by Company Wayne McGregor (long version).” *Youtube*, uploaded by

- StudioWayneMcGregor, Jun. 29, 2012. <https://youtu.be/fPHDb6ylhVY>.
- Foulkes, Julia L. *Modern Bodies: Dance and American Modernism from Martha Graham to Alvin Ailey*. Chapel Hill: The University of North Carolina Press, 2002. Print.
- Graham, Martha. *Blood Memory*. 1st ed. New York, NY: Doubleday, 1991. Print.
- Gibbens, Sarah. "The Atlantic Ocean-Facts and Information." *Environment*, National Geographic, May 4 2021, <https://www.nationalgeographic.com/environment/article/atlantic-ocean>.
- "Infra.", directed by Jonathan Haswell., produced by Roland Ott., Opus Arte, 2011. Alexander Street, <https://video.alexanderstreet.com/watch/Infra>.
- "Kairos by Wayne McGregor." *Youtube*, uploaded by Alvin Ailey American Dance Theater, Nov. 15, 2018, https://youtu.be/YftK_SPxCM0.
- "Martha Graham (01 A Dancer's World)." *Youtube*, uploaded by Benjamín Slavutzky, Apr. 24, 2020, <https://youtu.be/HNHHNz93Ucc>.
- "Martha Graham in Lamentation." *Youtube*, uploaded by Martha Graham Dance Company, Apr. 26, 2017, <https://youtu.be/I-lcFwPJUXQ>.
- "Paul Taylor.(Brief Article)." *American Theatre* 29.10 (2012): 17–. Print.
- "Paul Taylor's Esplanade-Part ⅓." *Youtube*, uploaded by danceonfilm, Jun. 6, 2010, <https://youtu.be/qyGWsGI7Ezo>.
- "Spectre - 1914 Martha Graham." *Youtube*, uploaded by PeiJu Chein-Pott, Sep. 26, 2017. <https://youtu.be/MW3e6FhfSLs>.
- "Revelations-Alvin Ailey American Dance Theater." *Youtube*, uploaded by Lincoln Center, Dec. 6, 2020, <https://youtu.be/kDXerubF4I4>.
- Roy, Sanjoy. "Step-by-Step Guide to Dance: Alvin Ailey." *The Guardian*, Guardian

News and Media, Sept. 9, 2010,

www.theguardian.com/stage/2010/sep/09/step-by-step-alvin-ailey.

“Wayne McGregor - Max Richter Remix - Zurich Opera House.” *Youtube*, uploaded by

Visual Affaire, Dec. 10, 2016, <https://youtu.be/YJ2h7bKsLnw>.

“Who was Isadora Duncan? Isadora Duncan Dances and Dance Technique.” *Youtube*,

uploaded by isadoraNow, Mar. 28, 2012, https://youtu.be/SPIN_gO5TOM.